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THE IMPORTANCE OF RIDDLES IN CHILDREN'S LITERATURE

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Abstract:

This article discusses the role and importance of riddles in English for elementary school students in children's literature, as well as the benefits of riddles in improving children's oral speech practice and developing mental abilities.

Keywords: pupils, literature, riddles, folk-art, methods

Children's literature is both a form of art and a means of education. Cultivating a well-rounded generation remains one of the key tasks for independent Uzbekistan. Artistic literature, especially children's literature, plays a significant role in this regard. Children's literature encompasses artistic, scientific, popular science, and journalistic works created for children and adolescents. Artistic works form the main part of this literature.

The spiritual revival process has raised the need to deeply study the poetic features of ancient and modern sources of Uzbek children's literature. Exploring the evolution of poetic thought in these works helps shed light on the formation of our nation's artistic thinking. The universal ideas depicted in such works serve to nurture the younger generation in the spirit of noble traditions established by our great ancestors and guide them toward spiritual growth.

Literary works for children should match their intellectual level, correspond to their age characteristics, inspire them toward high ideals, and motivate them to pursue noble deeds. The themes should be clear, interesting, and simple. Children's literature encourages patriotism, respect for parents, and good behavior. Only high-quality artistic works can meet these requirements, which is why such books are also significant from a pedagogical perspective.

The best books by writers teach the young generation a proper outlook on life, instill love for their homeland and labor, and nurture loyalty to their time, inspiring them to become worthy citizens. Books help shape a child's worldview,

build character, foster a love for science, and introduce them to the history, culture, and achievements of our people.

Another feature of children's literature is its dynamic and action-packed nature. This feature demands interesting, quick-paced, and imaginative storytelling. Taking into account the reader's age is one of the main characteristics of children's literature. For instance, for preschoolers, the narrative often revolves around the simple conflicts of good and evil, while for adolescents, the literature begins to explore the psychology of complex characters in real-life situations.

The development of children's literature in most nations is closely linked to educational reform and enlightenment movements. The stabilization of Uzbek children's literature dates back to the second half of the 19th century and the early 20th century, during the enlightenment movement. Educators like Saidrasul Aziziy, Munavvarqori, Abdulla Avloni, and Hamza Hakimzoda Niyoziy created dozens of alphabets and reading books for "new method" Uzbek schools, which are considered bright examples of children's literature.

Children's literature combines artistry and enlightenment, serving to educate the younger generation in the spirit of human virtues. The developmental principles of children's literature at all times are primarily characterized by educational and moral objectives.

Folk oral literature has been an inexhaustible source for written literature, influencing its emergence and development. It reflects the experiences of life and labor, deeply intertwined with cultural and social conditions.

Folk tales, songs, riddles, proverbs, and tongue twisters constitute a significant part of oral literature for preschoolers.

Riddles are one of the oldest and richest genres of folk oral literature. They embody the traditions, ethics, and aesthetic views of the people. A riddle describes an object's characteristics in an implicit, enigmatic way. The answer to a riddle lies in identifying the object based on questions like "what?" or "who?".

For example:

"At night, you see it as embers; by morning, it's gone."

(The star)

Children, in particular, find riddles intriguing and enjoy solving them. The topics of riddles are drawn from observable phenomena and objects in daily life, expressed through analogies.

For example:

"Underground is a golden stake, nourishing everyone."

(The carrot)

Such examples illustrate how riddles enhance imagination and learning.

The development of children's literature in Uzbekistan is greatly enriched by artistic translations from global children's literature, expanding the worldview of young readers and acquainting them with the customs, lifestyles, and aspirations of other nations.

References:

1. Mamasoli Jumaboyev: Uzbek Children's Literature. Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 2002, pp. 9–18.
2. Mamasoli Jumaboyev: Uzbek and Foreign Children's Literature. Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 2002, pp. 4–5.

